

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22

Estimate of soil hydraulic properties from disc infiltrometer three-dimensional infiltration curve. Numerical analysis and field application

B. Latorre ^{a*}, C. Peña ^a, L., Lassabatere^b, R. Angulo-Jaramillo ^b, D. Moret-Fernández ^a

^a Departamento de Suelo y Agua, Estación Experimental de Aula Dei, Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC), PO Box 13034, 50080 Zaragoza, Spain

^b Université de Lyon; UMR5023 Laboratoire d'Ecologie des Hydrosystèmes Naturels et Anthropisés; Université Lyon 1; ENTPE; CNRS; 3, rue Maurice Audin, 69518 Vaulx-en-Velin, France

* Corresponding author. E-mail: borja.latorre@csic.es Tel.: (+34) 976 71 60 42

1 **Abstract**

2 Based on the analysis of Haverkamp et al. (1994), this paper presents a new technique to
3 estimate the soil hydraulic properties (sorptivity, S , and hydraulic conductivity, K) from the
4 full-time cumulative infiltration curves. The proposed method, which will be named as the
5 Numerical Solution of the Haverkamp equation (NSH), was validated on 12 synthetic soils
6 simulated with HYDRUS-3D. The K values used to simulate the synthetic curves were
7 compared to those estimated with the NSH method. A procedure to detect and remove the
8 effect of the contact sand layer on the cumulative infiltration curve was also developed. A
9 sensitivity analysis was performed using the water level measurement as uncertainty source and
10 the procedure was evaluated considering different infiltration times and data noise (e.g. air-
11 bubbling in the infiltrometer). The good correlation between the K used in HYDRUS-3D to
12 model the infiltration curves and those obtained by the NSH method ($R^2=0.98$) indicates this
13 technique is robust enough to estimate the soil hydraulic conductivity from complete
14 infiltration curves. The numerical procedure to detect and remove the influence of the contact
15 sand layer on the K and S estimates resulted to be robust and efficient. A negative effect of the
16 curve infiltration noise on the K estimate was observed. The results showed that infiltration
17 time was an important factor to estimate K . Smaller values of K or lower uncertainty required
18 longer infiltration times. In a second step, the technique was tested in field conditions on 266
19 different soils at saturation conditions, using a 10 cm diameter disc infiltrometer. The NSH
20 method was compared to the standard differentiated linearization procedure (DL), which
21 estimates the hydraulic parameters using the simplified Haverkamp et al. (1994) equation, valid
22 only for short to medium times. Compared to DL, NSH was considerably less affected by the
23 infiltration bubbling and the contact sand layer, and allowed more robust estimates of K and S .
24 Although comparable S values were obtained with both methods, the NSH technique, which is
25 not limited to short times, resulted in more accurate and robust estimates for K . This paper

1 demonstrates the NSH method is a significant advance to estimate of the soil hydraulic
2 properties from the transient water flow.

3
4 **Keywords:** Soil hydraulic properties; Sorptivity; Hydraulic conductivity; Cumulative
5 infiltration; Contact sand layer; Transient water flow.

6

7 **1. Introduction**

8 *In situ* determination of soil hydraulic properties (sorptivity, S , and hydraulic conductivity, K)
9 is a fundamental requirement of physically based models describing field infiltration and runoff
10 processes. Over the last two decades, the tension disc infiltrometers (Perroux and White, 1988)
11 have become popular devices for *in situ* estimates of K and S . This instrument consists of a disc
12 base covered by a membrane, a graduated water-supply reservoir and a bubbling tower with a
13 moveable air-entry tube that imposes the pressure head at the cloth base. The cumulative
14 infiltration curve is measured from the water level drop in the reservoir. The diameter of the
15 disc base can vary from the 25 cm proposed by Perroux and White (1988) to the 3.2 cm used
16 by Madsen and Chandler (2007) for microtopography studies. Correct measurements of the
17 water infiltration with the tension infiltrometer require the disc base to be completely in contact
18 with the soil surface. To achieve this connection, Perroux and White (1988) recommended
19 trimming any vegetation within the sample to ground level and covering the soil with a material
20 with high hydraulic conductivity (contact sand layer). Although this procedure allows
21 infiltration measurements in most field situations, the water initially stored in the contact layer
22 alters the cumulative infiltration curve and, consequently, the estimation of K and S (Angulo-
23 Jaramillo et al., 2000). In those cases, the influence of the contact layer should be removed.
24 More recently, Sporgova et al. (2009) showed that the cumulative infiltration noise induced by
25 the bubbling in the infiltrometer reservoir can have a significant effect on the K estimation.

1 The soil hydraulic properties are calculated by analysing the cumulative water-infiltration
2 curve. Several methods to estimate the soil hydraulic properties have been proposed.: (i)
3 methods based on the Wooding (1968) equation, which uses steady-state data (Smettem and
4 Clothier, 1989; Ankeny et al., 1991; Reynolds and Elrick, 1991), (ii) methods based on the
5 transient state data (e.g. Vandervaere et al., 2000) and (ii) methods which combine both
6 transient and steady states, like BEST methods (Lassabatere et al., 2006; Yilmaz et al., 2010).
7 Compared to the standard steady-state water flow method, the transient water flow procedure,
8 that requires shorter experiments, involves smaller sampled soil volumes and more
9 homogeneous initial water distribution (Angulo-Jaramillo et al., 2000), which leads to better
10 estimates and better representativeness of the local hydraulic properties.

11 These are the reasons why we do not address steady state methods in this paper. Several
12 model have been developed to estimate the soil hydraulic parameters from the transient water
13 flow (Warrick and Broadbridge, 1992; Zhang, 1998). Haverkamp et al. (1994) obtained a
14 quasi-exact equation describing the three-dimensional unsaturated cumulative infiltration curve
15 for disc infiltrometers. Lassabatere et al. (2009) evaluated this equation with respect to their
16 ability to reproduce numerically generated cumulative infiltration from 10 cm radius disc
17 sources for four soils (sand, loam, silt and silty clay), and observed that the quasi-exact
18 formulation was suitable for sand, loam and silt soils when their soil-dependent and saturation-
19 independent shape parameters, γ and β , were properly chosen (between 0.75 and 1 and 0.3 and
20 1.7, respectively). Due to relative the complexity of this equation, Haverkamp et al. (1994)
21 proposed a simplified version, which allows estimating K and S using linear fitting techniques.
22 Vandervaere et al. (2000) compared the existing methods to analyse the transient state of the
23 simplified Haverkamp et al. (1994) equation (for more details, see theory section). They
24 concluded that the DL (for Derivative Linearization) method, which consists in a linear fit of a
25 the derivative of the cumulative infiltration data with respect to the square root of time, allowed

1 the best estimations of K and S when contact sand layer was used. However, these methods,
2 like the DL method, are only applicable for short to medium time and can be questioned when
3 steady state is reached too quickly, e.g. when infiltration is controlled by capillary forces
4 (Angulo-Jaramillo et al., 2000).

5 This work proposes an inverse analysis of the complete Haverkamp et al. (1994) equation
6 (Numerical Solution of the Haverkamp equation, NSH) to estimate the soil hydraulic properties
7 from the cumulative infiltration curve measured with a disc infiltrometer. Due to the multiple
8 tension methods used in the infiltrometry technique require long infiltration measurements, and
9 the objective of this work is optimising the field measurements, only infiltration measurements
10 at saturation conditions were considered. This technique accounts for the effect of a sandy layer
11 embedded below the infiltrometer on cumulative infiltration, and removes its impact on
12 estimates. The procedure was validated with regards both analytically generated data and field
13 experiments for the case of water infiltration with zero pressure head at surface. At first, the
14 water infiltration was computed for the case of zero water pressure head at surface and dry
15 initial state for 12 different synthetic soils, using HYDRUS-2D. This numerical data were
16 analyzed with the NSH method and the estimated hydraulic values were compared to the
17 original ones. The effect of noise on data (e.g. due to air bubbling in the Mariotte reservoir of
18 the infiltrometer) and the consequences on the quality of NSH estimates were also numerically
19 assessed. In a second step, the NSH method was evaluated under field conditions and tested on
20 266 experimental infiltration curves. The results were compared to the DL procedure, which
21 can be considered as a reference method for the analysis of the transient state of infiltration.
22 The influence of the infiltration curves noise and the effect of the contact sand layer on the K
23 and S estimates was evaluated and discussed for all methods.

24

25 **2. Theory: Infiltration equation**

1 The 1-D cumulative infiltration, $I_{1D}(t)$, is described by the quasi-exact equation, derived by
 2 Haverkamp et al. (1990) from the Richards equation:

$$3 \quad \frac{2(K_0 - K_n)^2}{S_0^2} t = \frac{2}{1 - \beta} \frac{(K_0 - K_n)(I_{1D} - K_n t)}{S_0^2} -$$

$$4 \quad \frac{1}{1 - \beta} \cdot \ln \left[\frac{1}{\beta} \exp \left(2\beta(K_0 - K_n)(I_{1D} - K_n t) / S_0^2 \right) + \frac{\beta - 1}{\beta} \right] \quad (1)$$

5
 6 where S_0 is the sorptivity for θ_0 ; K_0 and K_n are the hydraulic conductivity values corresponding
 7 to θ_0 and θ_n , respectively; and β is defined as an integral shape parameter.

8 The 3-D cumulative infiltration, $I_{3D}(t)$, from a surface disc source can be expressed by the
 9 1-D equation and an additional time linear term (Smettem et al., 1994):

$$10 \quad I_{3D} = I_{1D} + \frac{\gamma S_0^2}{R_D(\theta_0 - \theta_n)} t \quad (2)$$

11 where R_D is the radius of the disc and γ is the proportionality constant. Substituting Eq.(2) into
 12 Eq.(1), the implicit 3-D infiltration equation is obtained (Haverkamp et al., 1990), valid for the
 13 entire time range:

$$14 \quad \frac{2(K_0 - K_n)^2}{S_0^2} t = \frac{2}{1 - \beta} \frac{(K_0 - K_n) \left[I_{3D} - K_n t - \gamma S_0^2 / ((\theta_0 - \theta_n) R_D) t \right]}{S_0^2} -$$

$$15 \quad \frac{1}{1 - \beta} \cdot \ln \left[\frac{1}{\beta} \exp \left(2\beta(K_0 - K_n) \left[I_{3D} - K_n t - \gamma S_0^2 / ((\theta_0 - \theta_n) R_D) t \right] / S_0^2 \right) + \frac{\beta - 1}{\beta} \right] \quad (3)$$

16
 17 This expression requires adequate values for the parameters γ and β . While in their earlier
 18 work, Haverkamp et al. (1994) proposed an average value of 0.75 for γ and 0.6 for β ,
 19 Lassabatere et al. (2009) concluded that the shape parameters were closer to those predicted by
 20 Fuentes et al. (1992), especially for β . This study proved that Eq.(3) can describe cumulative
 21 infiltrations in sand, loam and silt soils but not for silty clay (a fine textured soil), due to its

1 hydraulic properties, which do not fulfil the conditions required for the validity of the quasi-
 2 exact formulation (see equations 2-4 in Lassabatere et al., 2009 for a detail of conditions to be
 3 fulfilled).

4 Haverkamp et al. (1994) established that, for short to medium time and assuming $K_n \rightarrow 0$,
 5 the 3D cumulative infiltration curve could be simplified to:

$$6 \quad I_{3D} = S_0 \sqrt{t} + \left[\frac{2-\beta}{3} K_0 + \frac{\gamma S_0^2}{R_D (\theta_n - \theta_0)} \right] t \quad (4)$$

7 which can be expressed as

$$8 \quad I_{3D} = C_1 \sqrt{t} + C_2 t \quad (5)$$

9 where

$$10 \quad C_1 = S_0 \quad (6)$$

11 and

$$12 \quad C_2 = \frac{2-\beta}{3} K_0 + \frac{\gamma S_0^2}{R_D (\theta_n - \theta_0)} \quad (7)$$

13 Applying the derivative operator to Eq.(4), the infiltration flux can be easily defined. In
 14 addition, the use algebraic combinations and the derivation with respect to the square root of
 15 time, lead to the following expression:

$$16 \quad q_{3D} = C_1 \frac{1}{2\sqrt{t}} + C_2 \quad (8)$$

$$17 \quad \frac{I_{3D}}{\sqrt{t}} = C_1 + C_2 \sqrt{t} \quad (9)$$

$$18 \quad \frac{dI_{3D}}{d\sqrt{t}} = C_1 + 2C_2 \sqrt{t} \quad (10)$$

19 The estimation of constants C_1 and C_2 is a prerequisite for the estimation of S_0 and K_0 . To do
 20 so, different procedures can be employed: (i) fitting Eq. (4) to experimental cumulative
 21 infiltration; (ii) fitting Eq. (8) to the experimental infiltration rate; (iii) performing the linear

1 regression of the dataset ($t^{0.5}, I/t^{0.5}$), or finally, (iv) performing the linear regression of the
2 dataset ($t^{0.5}, dI/dt^{0.5}$). These methods were referred to as CI for cumulative infiltration, IF for
3 Infiltration Flux, CL for Cumulative Linearization and DL for Derivative Linearization
4 (Vandervaere et al., 2000). According to these authors, only CL and DL technique allow
5 revealing and eliminating the influence of the sand contact layer at the beginning of
6 experiments. This effect can have negative effects on parameter estimations if not taken into
7 account. Once C_1 and C_2 are known, S_0 and K_0 can easily be inferred using equations (6) and
8 (7). It must be quoted that Eq.(4) is valid only for short to medium times, because it
9 corresponds to a simplification of Eq.(3) developed under this assumption (Haverkamp et al.,
10 1994). In this article, we focus on the DL method, which taking into account the short to
11 medium infiltration time, is considered as a reference method for analysis of transient state
12 infiltration data.

13

14 **3. Material and methods**

15 *3.1. Numerical analysis*

16 The numerical details of the proposed method are described in the following section. The
17 approach is based on the Haverkamp et al. (1994) equation to describe the full-time cumulative
18 infiltration curve. This equation does not have an explicit analytical solution and must be
19 solved numerically resolving equation (3). The hydraulic parameters are then estimated fitting
20 the theoretical curve to the experimental cumulative infiltration data. This process consists on a
21 global optimization that explores the parameter space (S and K) looking for the best fit between
22 the two curves, i.e. experimental data and implicit model. Details to account for the effect of
23 the contact sand layer on the cumulative infiltration curve are also given. Finally, a sensitivity
24 analysis was performed using the water level measurement as uncertainty source to account for
25 the effect of the noise due to air bubbling in the reservoir

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24

3.1.1. Numerical solution

In order to evaluate the 3-D cumulative infiltration equation, $I_{3D}(t)$, Eq.(3) must be solved by numerical analysis. Considering a single time value, t , and assuming known soil parameters, Eq.(3) can be rearranged as an infiltration function:

$$f(I) = 0 \tag{11}$$

The problem to solve $I_{3D}(t)$ is reduced to find the root of the $f(I)$ function. To this end, the simple and robust bisection method was used (Burden et al., 1985). The procedure defines an interval, $[I_1, I_2]$, where the function $f(I)$ takes opposite signs. The interval is then divided until the solution converges within a desired accuracy. To initiate the calculation, the start value for I_1 was set to zero and the initial value for I_2 was greater than the maximum expected infiltration. The algorithm was iteratively applied until a tolerance value (ε) of 10^{-3} was achieved:

$$I_2 - I_1 > \varepsilon \frac{I_1 + I_2}{2} \tag{12}$$

Large differences between nonlinear terms in Eq.(3) can lead to spurious solutions due to inaccurate results of fixed-precision arithmetic. To this end, the GMP (GNU Multiple Precision Arithmetic Library) library (Granlund, 2004) was used with 128 precision bits. Figure 1 shows an example of synthetic cumulative infiltration curves calculated for three of the studied synthetic soils (sand and loam and silt soils in Table 1).

3.1.2. Inverse analysis

Hydraulic parameters (sorptivity, S , and hydraulic conductivity, K) are estimated by minimizing an objective function, Q , that represents the difference between the implicit model Eq.(3) and the experimental cumulative infiltration data:

1
$$Q = \sum_{i=1}^n ((I_i - I(K, S, t_i)) \Delta t_i)^2 \quad (13)$$

2 where n is the number of measured (I, t) values. To this end, a brute-force search (Horst and
3 Romeijn, 2002) was employed, enumerating all possible candidates of the hydraulic parameters
4 to a certain precision and selecting the best result. This reference method, that requires
5 considerable computing power, was used to study the properties of the solution space and lead
6 to more efficient inverse methods. The γ and β values used in the analysis were fixed at their
7 values by default i.e. 0.75 and 0.6, respectively (Haverkamp et al., 1994).

8

9 *3.1.3. Sand-layer effect*

10 To ensure contact between the soil and the disc base, a sand layer is commonly placed on the
11 surface. However, the water stored in the sand influences the cumulative infiltration curve,
12 contradicts the homogeneity assumption of Eq.(1) and invalids the hydraulic parameters
13 obtained by the inverse analysis (Angulo-Jaramillo et al., 2000) (standard technique). A new
14 procedure to omit the influence of the contact sand layer (layered flow analysis) on the K and S
15 estimation is proposed. This consists of a layered flow model that assumes the water does not
16 infiltrate into the soil until the sand layer is completely saturated. After this early stage,
17 infiltration is assumed to occur as if the sand layer were inexistent with no flow impedance by
18 the highly conductive sand. Under these assumptions, the effect of sand can be considered just
19 as a delay of time and volume before water infiltration in the soil. Then, the effect of the
20 contact layer can be removed by finding the sand infiltration time (and its corresponding water
21 volume), that corresponds to the time required for water to fill in the sand, and shifting the
22 experimental data to the origin (in time and water volume). To account for such a shift in
23 infiltration time and volume, the proposed algorithm is based on the adaptation Eq.(13) to the
24 layered flow problem as follows. For any set of infiltration data, several values are considered

1 for sand infiltration times and volumes, leading to the definition of a collection of infiltration
2 curves as a function of sand infiltration and volume. Each curve is shifted in time and in
3 volume before being analyzed through the minimization of the objective function, Eq. (13).
4 This steps allows the selection of the hydraulic parameters that provide the best fitted. The
5 corresponding curve and values for sand infiltration time and volume are selected. This
6 approach captures the portion of the curve that best fits Eq.(3) and removes the sand layer
7 effect. The range of the proposed infiltration sand time values was fixed between 0 and 5
8 seconds every 0.1 s.

9

10 *3.1.4. Synthetic infiltration curves*

11 Infiltration experiments were simulated using HYDRUS-3D model (Simunek et al., 1999),
12 considering 12 different soils types (Table 1). Water retention curves were characterized using
13 the van Genuchten (1980) model with Mualem condition. We considered the Mualem model
14 for unsaturated hydraulic conductivity (Mualem, 1976). The soil volume was discretized as a
15 cylinder (radius of 25 cm and depth of 25 cm), covering the axisymmetric plane with a 2-D
16 rectangular mesh of 100×900 cells. The vertical cell size was variable to obtain more detail
17 near the surface, ranging from 0.003 cm on the top to 0.3 cm on the bottom. Maximum and
18 minimum time steps were fixed at 0.05 s and 10^{-4} s, respectively. Previous numerical analysis
19 demonstrated that, under this discretization, the solution is grid independent.

20 A base disc infiltrometer of 10 cm radius was represented as a constant pressure head
21 boundary on the corresponding cells, whereas the rest of the soil surface was treated as
22 atmospheric boundary with no flux. A null pressure head was considered as bottom boundary.
23 The lateral and the bottom boundaries of the soil cylinder were considered as no flux
24 boundaries, condition that is valid if the water does not reach these regions. The initial soil
25 water content was close to the residual water content to satisfy $\theta_n < 0.25 \theta_s$ that is required for

1 the validity of Eq.(1). The simulations run up to 50 mm water infiltration. This allowed
2 obtaining a fixed precision in the soil hydraulic parameters estimation.

3 To validate the method that removes the influence of the contact layer, simulations were
4 repeated on the same soils considering a 5 mm sand layer (with the same radius as the disc
5 base) placed on the surface. These new numerical data were used for the inversion procedure
6 using the layered flow option to assess the capability of the proposed procedure to find the sand
7 infiltration time and volumes. Hydraulic properties of the contact sand layer are shown in Table
8 1.

9

10 *3.1.5. Hydraulic stability*

11 Air bubbling in the water reservoir can affect the measurement of the cumulative infiltration.
12 To study the influence of air bubbling on the hydraulic parameter estimation, a synthetic noise
13 was added to the synthetic infiltration curves calculated for the previous step (see above). A
14 reference synthetic noise was extracted from the analysis of real experimental data used by
15 Moret-Fernández et al. (2013a). To do so, the bubbling effect was extracted by comparing the
16 experimental and the corresponding theoretical curves, fitted to Eq.(3) through an inverse
17 procedure. Statistical analysis of the difference between model and experimental data
18 demonstrated that the resulting noise could be described by a normal distribution. Three
19 increasing noise levels, corresponding to standard deviation values of 0.5, 1, and 2 mm, were
20 incorporated to the simulated infiltration curves (Table 1). According to our experience with
21 the disc infiltrometry technique, the selected standard deviation values cover most observed
22 field conditions.

23

24 *3.2. Field experiments*

25 *3.2.1. Experimental design*

1 The NSH method was tested on experimental infiltration curves recorded in laboratory, two
2 different sands (Table 2), and in semiarid dry lands of the central Ebro Basin (north-eastern
3 Spain). The average annual precipitation of the experimental fields ranges between 313 and
4 350 mm and the average annual air temperature ranges between 13.3 and 14.5 °C. The
5 experimental fields were located in the municipalities of Peñaflo, Codo, Belchite, Leciñena,
6 Sariñena and Bujaraloz. The lithology of the fields is gypseous alternating with non-gypseous
7 areas. The traditional land use is an agro-pastoral system involving rainfed agriculture and
8 extensive sheep grazing. The cropping system is a traditional cereal–fallow rotation, which
9 involves a long fallow period of 16–18 months, running from June–July to November–
10 December of the following year.

11 Five different contrasted soil managements were considered: ungrazed (NG) and grazed
12 (GR) uncultivated lands, and cultivated soil under conventional (CT), reduce (RT) and no-
13 tillage (NT) treatments. The NG and GR treatments were located on uncultivated soils at
14 Leciñena, Belchite, Codo and Sariñena municipalities. The grazing intensity in the GR fields
15 was < 1 livestock unit ha^{-1} year^{-1} . Natural vegetation cover is spatially discontinuous where
16 vegetation is distributed in patches with wide open inter-patch areas. Measurements were
17 performed on the bare soil of the inter-patch areas (Moret-Fernández et al. 2011). Agricultural
18 fields were placed in Peñaflo and Bujaraloz. Experimental field in Peñaflo was located in the
19 dryland research farm of the Estación Experimental de Aula Dei (CSIC) in the province of
20 Zaragoza. The study was conducted on a large block of plots within a long-term conservation
21 tillage experiment initiated in 1989. The field was in winter barley (*Hordeum vulgare L.*)-
22 fallow crop system. Three different tillage treatments were examined: conventional tillage
23 (CT), reduced tillage (RT) and no-tillage (NT). The CT and RT treatment consisted of
24 mouldboard (40 cm depth) and chisel (30 cm depth) ploughing of fallow plots in early spring,
25 respectively. NT used exclusively herbicides (glyphosate) for weed control throughout the

1 fallow season. All measurements were done in fallowed soils (F) and consisted of soils in the
2 aggregation status after six to eight months of fallow, prior to any primary tillage operations.
3 Details about the field characteristics of Peñaflores can be found in Moret and Arrúe (2007).
4 Measurements in Bujaraloz were conducted on commercial agricultural fields under CT
5 management. Three different soil structural conditions were considered: freshly moldboard
6 tilled (MB), cropped (C) and fallowed soils. Infiltration measurements in MB were performed
7 on freshly tilled soils just after a pass with a moldboard plow (in the spring of the 18-months
8 fallow period), before any rainfall event. The C treatment corresponded to soils in the
9 aggregation status for the last stages of winter cereal development (May–June). The soil under
10 F did not present adventitious plants and was partially covered (>20%) with winter cereal crop
11 residues. Measurements in C and F were performed between crop lines. A total of 16 sampling
12 points under MB and C and 24 for F (Table 2) were selected in Bujaraloz. All measurements
13 were conducted on nearly level areas (slope 0–2%) between February 2000 and April 2001,
14 and February 2009 and October 2010. Details about the field characteristics of Bujaraloz can be
15 found in Moret-Fernández et al. (2013c).

16

17 *3.2.2. Soil hydraulic properties estimation from field measurements*

18 All samplings for soil texture properties per experimental field were taken from the 0–10 cm
19 depth soil layer. The samples, one replication per field, were homogenized and sieved up to
20 2mm for the subsequent laboratory analyses. The soil particle size distribution and related
21 textural parameters were determined using the laser diffraction technique (COULTER LS230).

22 The soil dry bulk density (ρ_b) measured within the 2–7 cm depth soil layer, after removing
23 the soil surface crust, was determined by the core method (Grossman and Reinsch, 2002)
24 (50mm diameter and 50mm height). One replication was taken per infiltration measurements.
25 The ρ_b values with mass water contents were subsequently used to determine the prior

1 volumetric water content and the saturated water contents needed to calculate the surface
2 hydraulic conductivity K_0 using Mualem capillary model.

3 The transient cumulative infiltration curves were measured with a Perroux and White (1988)
4 model tension disc infiltrometer. The diameter disc and internal diameter of the water reservoir
5 tower was 100 mm and 34 mm, respectively. Two different base discs were used: (i) a
6 conventional disc (C_{DB}) which base was covered with a tightened nylon cloth of 20- μ m mesh
7 and uses contact sand layer between the soil surface and the base disc; and (ii) a malleable base
8 disc (M_{DB}), which base was covered with a loosened malleable nylon cloth of 20- μ m mesh
9 filled with 100 g of coarse sand (1–1.5 mm grain size; 0.5-cm-thick layer, approximately)
10 (Moret-Fernández et al., 2013b). This alternative design allows adapting the base disc to the
11 soil surface without using contact sand layer.

12 The infiltration measurements were taken on areas cleared of large clods and crop residue.
13 These included infiltration measurements on the soil surface crust and on the 1–10 cm depth
14 soil layer, after removing the surface crust (Table 2). For the conventional disc (C_{DB}) a thin
15 layer (< 1 cm thick) of commercial sand (80–160 μ m grain size and an air-entry value between
16 -1 and -1.5 kPa), with the same diameter as the disc base, was poured onto the soil surface.
17 The M_{DB} disc was directly placed on the soil surface. A total of 266 cumulative infiltration
18 curves were recorded (Table 2). Measurements in Bujaraloz, Belchite, Codo, Leciñena and
19 Sariñena were done with a C_{DB} disc, and infiltration measurements in Peñaflores with the C_{DB}
20 and M_{DB} base (Table 2). All measurements were performed at 0 cm of pressure head. The water
21 infiltration was measured from the drop of water level in the reservoir tower, which was
22 automatically monitored with ± 0.5 psi differential pressure transducer (PT) (Microswitch,
23 Honeywell) (Casey and Derby, 2002). The scanning time interval was 10 seconds. Infiltration
24 measurements lasted between 8 and 15 min. At the end of infiltration, a wet soil sample was
25 taken to estimate the final gravimetric water content (W). The final volumetric water content

1 needed to estimate the soil hydraulic properties was calculated as the product between W and
2 ρ_b .

3 The influence of the water reservoir bubbling on the DL and NSH methods was evaluated.
4 To this end, four representative curves with different noise ranges, two with low and high
5 noise, respectively, were selected. These correspond to infiltration experiments concluded in
6 the Bujaraloz, Peñaflor and Codo fields (Table 4). The four infiltration measurements were
7 conducted on the 1-10 cm depth soil layer, and contact sand layer was employed. In a second
8 step, the influence of the contact sand layer on the DL and NSH methods was also studied.

9 The S and K estimated with the NSH method for the 266 measured field infiltration curves
10 were subsequently compared to the corresponding values estimated with the DL procedure
11 (when available). To prevent subjective decisions with DL, the following procedure was
12 established:

- 13 (i) time interval of 10 s between two successive measures;
- 14 (ii) removal of the first points which correspond to water infiltration in the sand layer ;
- 15 (iii) total infiltration time was < 150 s.

16 Comparison between DL and NSH involved the following conditions:

- 17 (i) Eq.(10) curves with regression coefficients $(R^2_{DL}) < 0.15$ were omitted. The
18 remaining curves $(R^2_{DL} > 0.15)$ were grouped in three sets: (a) $0.15 > R^2_{DL} > 0.60$,
19 (b) $0.6 > R^2_{DL} > 0.70$ and (c) $R^2_{DL} > 0.70$
- 20 (ii) no negative K or S results were considered;

21

22 **4. Results and discussion**

23 **4.1. Numerical analysis**

24 *4.1.1. Method validation*

1 An excellent fitting was observed between synthetic and modelled cumulative infiltration
2 curves for the case of infiltration with no sand layer (Fig. 2a; Table 3). The objective function
3 presents a unique and narrow minimum around the optimal hydraulic properties values (Fig 2b
4 and c). These results show that, for the case depicted in Figure 2, estimates can be properly
5 identified for both sorptivity (S) and hydraulic conductivity (K), and that the estimates are close
6 to the targeted values. Overall, NSH method provided accurate estimates for all cases.
7 Estimated hydraulic conductivities and reference values present high correlation ($R^2 = 0.95$)
8 (Fig. 3), indicating the ability of the method to estimate K from transient infiltration curves.
9 Although Lassabatere et al. (2009) observed that the quasi-exact formulation was suitable when
10 the soil-dependent and saturation-independent shape parameters, γ and β , are properly chosen,
11 our results showed that the average values proposed by Haverkamp et al (1994) gave
12 acceptable results.

13 As a second step, we inverted the data obtained for the layered profile (sand + soils) with the
14 NSH method, based on the standard analysis without the layered flow analysis. We aimed at
15 quantifying the impact of the sandy layer onto the quality of estimates in the case its negative
16 effect is not considered. As showed in Figure 4, the first case concerns the inversion of
17 synthetic cumulative infiltration obtained for the soil alone. The synthetic data are accurately
18 fitted by the model and the estimates provided by the NSH –standard analysis method are
19 accurate: $1.33 \cdot 10^{-2}$ versus $1.20 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ for saturated hydraulic conductivity. The embedment
20 of the sand increase the cumulative infiltration (\square versus \circ , in Figure 4).

21 The analysis of the synthetic cumulative infiltration with the NSH-standard analysis leads to a
22 poor fit with underestimation of the data for short times. Related estimates are far from targeted
23 values, specifically for the saturated hydraulic conductivity with a value of $4.37 \cdot 10^{-6}$ versus
24 $1.20 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ m s}^{-1}$. Finally, the use of layered flow analysis permits an accurate fit of the data
25 (Figure 4) and give an appropriate value for estimates with $2.11 \cdot 10^{-2}$ versus $1.20 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ m s}^{-1}$.

1 Similar results were obtained for the other cases. Inaccurate results are obtained when the
2 standard analysis is applied to synthetic curves obtained for soils with contact sand layer (Fig.
3 3; Table 2). However, these errors vanished when the layered flow model is used (Fig. 3; Table
4 2), where a strong correlation ($R^2 = 0.93$) between the original and estimated K was observed
5 (Fig. 3). These results show the NSH with layered flow analysis allows the use of infiltrometer
6 with sand layer and a proper analysis of the data obtained in such configuration. These results
7 validate the proposed method against synthetic data. For the case of soil 10, no results are
8 available since the numerical calculation of water cumulative infiltration could not be
9 determined, due HYDRUS numerical convergence errors.

10

11 *4.1.2. Sensitivity and uncertainty*

12 Infiltration measurements are affected by several sources of uncertainty (i.e. water level
13 measurement, contact sand layer, effective disc radius, etc.), which may propagate its
14 variability to the hydraulic parameters estimates. In our case, only the source of uncertainty due
15 to water level measurement (± 0.5 mm) was considered.

16 The water level measurement uncertainty depends on the reservoir diameter. Two different
17 diameters (3.4 and 6.0 cm) were considered, resulting in increasing uncertainties for larger
18 diameters (Fig. 5). A sensitivity analysis was performed, around each inverse solution, as part
19 of a first order uncertainty analysis. The change of the objective function (Eq.13) associated to
20 the uncertainty source was first calculated and transported to the inverse analysis parameter
21 space, estimating the variability of the results (Fig. 5). It is clearly shown that larger water
22 reservoir diameters result in an increase in measurement errors and thus widen the confidence
23 intervals for all estimates (K and S). For this case, (soil #12, Figure 5), the confidence intervals
24 are $(2.01 \cdot 10^{-2}, 2.26 \cdot 10^{-2})$ and $(1.78 \cdot 10^{-2}, 2.52 \cdot 10^{-2}, \text{mm s}^{-1})$, for K , respectively for a diameter of
25 6.0 and 3.4 cm. It can be noted while the range of confidence intervals are impacted, the

1 estimated values are not affected by this factor. Similar results were found for all the other
2 soils.

3 The influence of the experiments duration on the estimates was also tested. Analysis of
4 Eq.(3) showed that the accuracy of the hydraulic properties estimation depends also on the
5 measurement time. Shorter infiltration times shift the optimal K values and widen the objective
6 function. This is illustrated for the case of Soil #12 in Fig. 6. In this case, if we consider a
7 desired precision in the measurements (here the same as for the infiltrometer with 3.4 cm in
8 diameter), the change in time duration changes both the range of the confidence interval and
9 the center of the interval (i.e. the estimation). Clearly, best estimates are obtained for longer
10 experiments, which means that proper estimations for hydraulic conductivity and sorptivity
11 require to wait long enough. The analysis was extended to all synthetic infiltration curves, to
12 determine the minimum infiltration time required to estimate the hydraulic parameters within a
13 certain relative accuracy (10 and 90%), by means of an iterative procedure (Fig. 7). The results
14 show that: (i) infiltration time needed to estimate the hydraulic properties within a fixed
15 uncertainty increases as the soil permeability decreases, and (ii) the S, which is mainly related
16 to the initial infiltration times (Angulo-Jaramillo et al., 2000), is less affected than K by the
17 infiltration time.

18 The NSH method appears interesting and promising since it uses the analytical expression
19 developed by Haverkamp et al. (1994) that is valid for all times. Thus, opposite to other
20 methods, this technique does not require the attainment of steady state, which can be quite time
21 consuming for some soils. Yet, these calculations show that time duration of the dataset to be
22 analyzed with the NSH method needs to be long enough. However, we consider that a constant
23 water infiltration volume can be better criteria to obtain fixed accuracy for all soils. For a 10
24 cm diameter disc infiltrometer, we have found that this volume is about 50 mm.

25

1 4.1.3. Bubbling effect

2 A satisfactory fitting of the different noisy curves was observed (Fig. 8a). Although the
3 objective function distribution around the optimal hydraulic properties values presents a unique
4 minimal value, the noisiest curves tended to increase the width of the wells and, accordingly,
5 the uncertainty of the estimations (Fig 8b and c), mostly for hydraulic conductivity (K). The
6 results showed that S was not affected by the noise level (Fig. 9a). Only the noisiest infiltration
7 curves had a significant influence on K, which optimal values differing from those calculated
8 from the original curves (Fig. 9b). These results prove that the NSH method allows to treat
9 even noisy data with no clear impact on the quality of estimates for both saturated hydraulic
10 conductivity and sorptivity.

11

12 4.2. Field testing

13 4.2.1. Water reservoir bubbling influence

14 The bubbling in the water supply reservoir during the infiltration experiments, which
15 perturbs the cumulative infiltration curves, had an important influence on the DL method. This
16 method could be satisfactorily applied only on low noisy infiltration curves (Fig. 10a and b). In
17 these cases, both DL and NSH procedures gave comparable K and S values (Table 4).
18 Increasing noise in the infiltration curves (Fig. 10c.2 and d.2), reduced the R^2 related to Eq.(10)
19 and prevented coherent estimates of K, which even gave negative values (Table 4). This
20 problem, which is due to Eq.(10) is very sensitive to anomalous changes in the infiltration
21 curve slopes, may be solved by increasing the infiltration time interval, smoothing the data, or
22 removing spurious pair of $\frac{dI}{d\sqrt{t}}$ vs. \sqrt{t} points. However, the subjectivity of this process, which
23 depends on the researcher experience, makes the DL method to be time-consuming and
24 subjective. This drawback of the DL method results from the derivation process which requires
25 an extreme precision of the data. This problem vanished with NSH, with the use of the full-

1 time cumulative infiltration curve, is significantly less affected by the infiltration noise (Fig.
2 10.1). The low RMSEs between the NSH modelled and experimental curves (Table 4) indicate
3 this method can satisfactorily be applied even in noisy infiltration curves. In addition, the
4 values for estimates seem plausible.

5

6 4.2.2. *Influence of the contact sand layer*

7 The water initially stored in the contact sand layer during the early stages of the infiltration
8 measurements makes a jump in the initial times of the cumulative infiltration curve (Fig. 10a
9 and 2b). As reported by Vandervaere et al. (2000), this sand infiltration time (t_{sand}) should be
10 removed from infiltration curve analysis to properly estimate the soil hydraulic properties.
11 Applied on low-noisy infiltration curves, the DL method allowed revealing and removing the
12 infiltration steps corresponding to the sand layer wetting (black points in Fig. 10.2). The
13 remaining data could be satisfactorily used to estimate the K and S (Table 4). A completely
14 different scenario was observed for noisy infiltration curves, where indistinguishable t_{sand}
15 values were observed (Fig. 10c.2 and d.2). In these cases, the difficulty to detect t_{sand} and the
16 subjectivity of this procedure makes the DL method to be inaccurate and uneasy to apply.
17 These limitations vanish when using the NSH method (Fig. 10 and Table 4), which numerical
18 approach automatically removes the t_{sand} infiltration steps and estimates K and S from the
19 remaining cumulative infiltration values.

20

21 4.2.3. *K and S estimates*

22 Over the 266 experimental infiltration curves, a total of 158 measurements (59%), with a
23 $R^2_{\text{DL}} < 0.15$, were omitted from the DL analysis. Such percentage indicate a high rate of failure.
24 From the remaining data, 87 curves (33%) presented a R^2_{DL} between 0.15 and 0.60, and only 21
25 measurements (8%) showed a $R^2_{\text{DL}} \geq 0.6$. These results indicate that only 40% of experimental

1 infiltration curves could be analysed by the DL method. Overall, the S estimated with DL was
2 well correlated to that calculated with NSH (Fig. 11a). This is due to the high infiltration rates
3 in the early infiltration stages providing accurate derivatives. A substantial worse K_{DL} vs K_{NSH}
4 correlation was observed. Only linearized infiltration curves with $R^2_{DL} > 0.7$ gave a satisfactory
5 K_{DL} vs K_{NSH} correlation ($R^2 = 0.96$) (Fig.11b). For the remaining measurements, a poorer K_{DL}
6 vs K_{NSH} correlation was found, where DL tended to overestimate K . Two reasons could explain
7 these results: (i) the DL method results are highly inaccurate for noisy infiltration curves (R^2_{DL}
8 < 0.6 .) (Fig. 10b); and (ii) the application of DL method is restricted to relatively short time
9 (i.e. 150s). As above demonstrated, the selection of longer datasets with NSH method, that
10 remain valid for all times, allows to increase the quality and accuracy of estimates and to
11 reduce uncertainty. The analysis of time duration of the experiments on the estimates of K and
12 S using the NSH method (Fig. 7) reveals that the infiltration time used in the field experiments
13 (ranged between 480 and 900 s) was in most cases insufficient to estimate K and S with a 10%
14 or 90% accuracy. In those cases, longer infiltration measurements should be recommended.

15

16 **5. Conclusions**

17 This paper describes, and evaluates under field conditions, a new numerical procedure (NSH)
18 to estimate the soil K and S from the cumulative infiltration curve of a disc infiltrometer using
19 the analytical equation developed by Haverkamp et al. (1994). This procedure also removes the
20 effect of the contact sand layer to improve the quality of estimates for K and S . The method was
21 satisfactorily validated on 12 synthetic infiltration curves simulated with HYDRUS-3D from
22 known soil hydraulic properties, including scenarios with contact sand layer. A sensitivity
23 analysis was conducted using the water level measurement as the source of uncertainty. The
24 effect of the infiltration curve noise (due to the bubbling in the infiltrometer) and the minimum
25 theoretical time to achieve accurate estimations were calculated and presented. The results

1 show that a constant water infiltration volume is a better criteria to obtain fixed accuracy for all
2 soils. For a 10 cm diameter disc infiltrometer, we have found that this volume is about 50 mm.
3 The method (NSH) was subsequently compared to the differential model (DL) on 266
4 infiltration measurements taken under different soil conditions. Compared to the DL procedure,
5 NSH allowed more robust estimates of K and S, independently on the infiltration curve noise
6 and the presence of contact sand layer between the soil surface and the base disc. The proposed
7 method has the advantage to work with raw cumulative data, instead of differentiated data and
8 to be valid for all times, which allow to consider large datasets. The results demonstrated that
9 the NSH method means a substantial advance to estimate the soil hydraulic properties from
10 transient water infiltration flows. However, new efforts should be done to include additional
11 disc infiltrometer uncertainty sources, such as effective disc radius, in the analysis.

12

13

14 **Acknowledgements**

15 This research was supported by the Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación of Spain (grant
16 AGL2010-22050-C03-02) and by the Aragón regional government and La Caixa (Grants:
17 2012/ GA LC 074). We would like to thank to Oussama Mounzer for his technical help to
18 develop this paper.

19

20 **References**

21 Angulo-Jaramillo R, Vandervaere JP, Roulier S, Thony JL, Gaudet JP, Vauclin, M. 2000. Field
22 measurement of soil surface hydraulic properties by disc and ring infiltrometers. A
23 review and recent developments. Soil Tillage Research 55: 1–29.

1 Ankeny, M.D., Ahmed, M., Kaspar, T.C., Horton, R., 1991. Simple field method determining
2 unsaturated hydraulic conductivity. *Soil Science Society of America Journal* 55, 467-
3 470.

4 Burden, R. L., Faires, J.D. 1985. *Numerical Analysis* (3rd ed.), PWS Publishers, ISBN 0-
5 87150-857-5.

6 Casey FXM, Derby NE. 2002. Improved design for an automated tension infiltrometer. *Soil*
7 *Science Society of America Journal* 66, 64–67.

8 Grossman, R. B., Reinsch, T. G. 2002. Bulk density and linear extensibility. *In*, *Methods of*
9 *Soil Analysis*. Part 4, pp. 201–205, in J. H. Dane and G. C. Topp, eds., SSSA Book 360
10 Series No. 5. Soil Science Society of America, Madison WI.

11 Fuentes, C., Haverkamp, R., Parlange, J. Y. 1992. Parameter constraints on closed-form soil
12 water relationships. *Journal of Hydrology* 134, 117-142.

13 Granlund, T. 2004. GNU MP: The GNU Multiple Precision Arithmetic Library, 4.1.4 ed.
14 <http://gmplib.org/>.

15 Haverkamp, R., Parlange, J.Y., Starr, J.L., Schmitz, G., Fuentes C. 1990, Infiltration under
16 ponded conditions: 3. A predictive equation based on physical parameters. *Soil Science*
17 149, 292–300.

18 Haverkamp R, Ross PJ, Smettem KRJ, Parlange JY. 1994. Three dimensional analysis of
19 infiltration from the disc infiltrometer. Part 2. Physically based infiltration equation.
20 *Water Resources Research* 30: 2931-2935.

21 Horst, R., Romeijn, H. E. (Eds.). 2002. *Handbook of global optimization* (Vol. 2). Springer
22 Science & Business Media.

23 Kodesová, R., Jirku, V., Kodes, V., Mühlhansellová, M., Nikodem, A., Zigova, A. 2011. Soil
24 structure and soil hydraulic properties of Haplic Luvisol used as arable land and
25 grassland. *Soil and Tillage Research* 111, 154–161.

- 1 Lassabatere L., Angulo-Jaramillo R., Soria Ugalde J. M., Cuenca R., Braud I., Haverkamp, R.
2 2006. Beerkan Estimation of Soil Transfer parameters through infiltration experiments –
3 BEST. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 70, 521-532.
- 4 Lassabatere, L., Angulo-Jaramillo, R., Soria-Ugalde, J.M., Simunek, J. Haverkamp, R. 2009.
5 Numerical evaluation of a set of analytical infiltration equations. *Water Resources*
6 *Research*, 45, doi:10.1029/2009WR007941.
- 7 Madsen, M.D., Chandler, D.G. 2007. Automation and use of mini disk infiltrometers. *Soil*
8 *Science Society of America Journal* 71, 1469-1472.
- 9 Moret, D., Braud, I., Arrúe, J.L. 2007. Water balance simulation of a dryland soil during fallow
10 under conventional and conservation tillage in semiarid Aragon, Northeast Spain. *Soil*
11 *and Tillage Research* 92, 251–263.
- 12 Moret-Fernández, D., Bueno, G., Pueyo, Y., Alados, C.L. 2011. Hydro-physical responses of
13 gypseous and non-gypseous soils to livestock grazing in a semi-arid region of NE Spain.
14 *Agricultural Water Management* 98, 1822-1827.
- 15 Moret-Fernández, Latorre, B., González-Cebolada, C. 2013a. Microflowmeter–tension disc
16 infiltrometer: Part II – Hydraulic properties estimation from transient infiltration rate
17 analysis. *Journal of Hydrology* 466-467, 159-166.
- 18 Moret-Fernández, D., Blanco, N., Martínez-Chueca, V., Bielsa, A. 2013b. Malleable disc base
19 for direct infiltration measurements using the tension infiltrometry technique.
20 *Hydrological Processes* 27, 275-283.
- 21 Moret-Fernández, D., Castañeda, C., Paracuellos, E., Jiménez, S., Herrero, J. 2013c. Hydro-
22 physical characterization of contrasting soils in a semiarid zone of the Ebro river valley
23 (NE Spain). *Journal of Hydrology* 486, 403-411.
- 24 Perroux KM, White I. 1988. Designs for disc permeameters. *Soil Science Society of America*
25 *Journal* 52, 1205–1215.

- 1 Reynolds, W.D., Elrick, D.E., 1991. Determination of hydraulic conductivity using a tension
2 infiltrometer. *Soil Science Society of America Journal* 55, 633–639.
- 3 Šimunek, J., Šejna, M., van Genuchten, M-Th. 1999. The HYDRUS-2D software package for
4 simulating the two-dimensional movement of water, heat, and multiple solutes in
5 variably-saturated media. Version 2.0. U.S. Salinity laboratory, Agricultural Research
6 Service, USDA, Riverside, California.
- 7 Špongrová, K., Kechavarzi, C., Dresser, M., Matula, S., Godwin, R.J. 2009. Development of an
8 automated tension infiltrometer for field use. *Vadose Zone Journal* 8, 810-817.
- 9 Špongrová, K., Matula, S., Kechavarzi, C., Dresser, M. 2010. Differences in topsoil properties
10 of a sandy loam soil under different tillage treatments. 19th World Congress of Soil
11 Science, Soil Solutions for a Changing World. Brisbane, Australia.
- 12 Smettem, K.R.J., Clothier, B.E., 1989. Measuring unsaturated sorptivity and hydraulic
13 conductivity using multi-disc permeameters. *Journal of Soil Science* 40, 563-568.
- 14 Smettem, K.R.J., Parlange, J.Y., Ross, P.J., Haverkamp, R., 1994. Three-dimensional analysis
15 of infiltration from the disc infiltrometer. Part 1. A capillary-based theory. *Water*
16 *Resources Research* 30, 2925-2929.
- 17 Vandervaere, J.P., Vauclin, M., Elrick, D.E., 2000. Transient Flow from Tension
18 Infiltrometers. Part 1. The two-parameter Equation. *Soil Science Society of America*
19 *Journal* 64, 1263-1272.
- 20 van Genuchten, M.T. 1980. A closed form equation for predicting the hydraulic conductivity of
21 unsaturated soils. *Soil Science Society of America Journal* 44, 892– 898.
- 22 Warrick, A.W., Broadbridge, P., 1992. Sorptivity and macroscopic capillary length
23 relationships. *Water Resources Research* 28, 427-431.
- 24 Wooding, R.A., 1968. Steady infiltration from a shallow circular pond. *Water Resources*
25 *Research* 4, 1259-1273.

- 1 Yilmaz D., Lassabatere L., Angulo R., Legret M. 2010. Hydrodynamic characterization of BOF
2 slags through adapted BEST method. *Vadoze Zone Journal*, 9 (1), 107-116.
- 3 Zhang, R. 1998. Estimating soil hydraulic conductivity and macroscopic capillary length from
4 disc infiltrometer. *Soil Science Society of America Journal* 62, 1513-1521.
- 5

Figures captions

Figure 1. Synthetic cumulative infiltration curves for sand, loam and silt soils (Table 1)

Figure 2. (a) Synthetic infiltration curve (circles) for a loam soil under no tillage treatment (Table 1; soil 12) and the corresponding fitted Eq.(3) curve (line), without contact sand layer, and the objective function distribution around the optimal values for (b) S and (c) K .

Figure 3. Correlation between the proposed K values (Table 1) and the estimations using Eq.(3) for the following scenarios: (○) NSH inversion of synthetic cumulative infiltrations into soils without sand layer and standard analysis, (□) NSH inversion of synthetic cumulative infiltrations into soils with sand layer and standard technique and (△)NSH inversion of synthetic cumulative infiltrations into soils with sand layer and layered flow analysis.

Figure 4. Synthetic curve for soil 12 (Table 1) and the corresponding fitted curves for the following scenarios: synthetic cumulative infiltration for the soil without sand layer (○) and standard analysis (—), synthetic cumulative infiltration for the soil with sand layer (□) analysed with the NSH standard technique (— · —) and or with NSH with layered flow analysis (— —). Black squares correspond to the estimated initial sand layer infiltration.

Figure 5. Estimation of the uncertainty for S and K estimations considering soil 12, two diameter reservoir of 3.4 and 6.0 mm.

1 **Figure 6.** Objective function distribution around the optimal values for S and K considering
2 soil 12 and infiltration times of 700 s (continuous line) and 100 s (discontinuous line).

3
4 **Figure 7.** Required infiltration time to estimate the hydraulic parameters within a relative
5 accuracy of 10 and 90%, considering a water level error source (± 0.5 mm) applied to a
6 1.6 cm diameter reservoir. Colours and contour levels denote the required infiltration
7 time in (base-10) logarithm seconds time, and K and S are plotted in (base-10) logarithm
8 scale.

9
10 **Figure 8.** Synthetic curves for soil 12 (Table 1) with three noise levels (normal distributions
11 with standard deviation of 0 (\circ), 0.5 (\triangle), 1 (\square), and 2 (\diamond) mm) and fitted cumulative
12 infiltration (a) and objective functions distribution around the optimal values for S (b)
13 and K (c).

14
15 **Figure 9.** Correlation between the original K (a) and S (b) values (Table 1) and the estimations
16 considering different noise level (normal distributions with standard deviation of 0.5
17 (\triangle), 1 (\square), and 2 (\diamond) mm). Error bars denote the uncertainty of the different results.

18
19 **Figure 10. a.1 to d.1)** Comparison between cumulative infiltration curves measured (points) in
20 four different fields (Table 2), and the corresponding 3D modelled curves simulated
21 from the hydraulic properties (Table 2) estimated with the DL (black discontinuous line)
22 and NSH (grey continuous line) methods; and **a.2 to d.2)** the DL method applied to the
23 corresponding soils. Black points denote the section of the linear fitting curve
24 corresponding to the contact sand layer.

25

1
2 **Figure 11.** Relationship between the soil sorptivity (S) (a) and hydraulic conductivity (K) (b)
3 estimated with the DL and NSH methods. Circles (○), triangles (△) and squares (□)
4 denote comparison between DL and NSH for $R^2_{DL} > 0.7$, $0.6 > R^2_{DL} > 0.7$, and $0.15 >$
5 $R^2_{DL} > 0.6$, respectively.

6

7

8

1

2 **Table 1.** Synthetic soils considered for the numerical study: soil textures, conditions and hydraulic parameters used in the HYDRUS-3D
 3 simulations.

Soil number	Soil texture	Soil conditions	θ_s	θ_{res}	α (cm)	n	K_s (mm s ⁻¹)	Reference
1	Sand	Sieved soil	0.43	0.04	0.145	2.68	$8.25 \cdot 10^{-2}$	Lassabatere et al. (2009)
2	Loam	Sieved soil	0.43	0.08	0.036	1.56	$2.88 \cdot 10^{-3}$	Lassabatere et al. (2009)
3	Silt	Sieved soil	0.46	0.03	0.016	1.37	$6.95 \cdot 10^{-4}$	Lassabatere et al. (2009)
4	Silty clay loam	Arable soil; Horizon Bt1	0.41	0.27	0.051	1.53	$9.36 \cdot 10^{-3}$	Kodesová et al. (2011)
5	Silty loam	Arable soil; Horizon C	0.38	0.01	0.026	1.18	$4.52 \cdot 10^{-3}$	Kodesová et al. (2011)
6	Silty loam	Grassland; Horizon A2	0.49	0.19	0.088	1.24	$8.18 \cdot 10^{-3}$	Kodesová et al. (2011)
7	Sandy loam soil	Conventional tillage	0.35	0.05	0.169	1.46	$6.98 \cdot 10^{-2}$	Špongrová et al. (2010)
8	Sandy loam soil	Direct drill	0.38	0.05	0.192	1.46	$8.35 \cdot 10^{-2}$	Špongrová et al. (2010)
9	Sandy loam soil	Conventional tillage wheel mark	0.36	0.05	0.110	1.68	$3.90 \cdot 10^{-2}$	Špongrová et al. (2010)
10	Loam soil	Conventional tillage	0.49	0.06	0.100	2.25	$3.00 \cdot 10^{-2}$	Moret et al. (2007)
11	Loam soil	Reduce tillage	0.49	0.07	0.091	2.24	$2.10 \cdot 10^{-2}$	Moret et al. (2007)
12	Loam soil	No tillage	0.42	0.09	0.033	2.21	$1.20 \cdot 10^{-2}$	Moret et al. (2007)

4

5

6

1 **Table 2.** Location, soil type, textural classification (USDA), soil management and number of infiltration measurements conducted
 2 in the different experimental fields.

Field	Soil	Textural classification	Soil status ¹	Treatments ²	N° of infiltration measurements			
					On SC ³ with CSL ⁴	On SC without CSL	On 0-10 layer with CSL	On 0-10 layer without CSL
Laboratory		Sand (250-500 µm)			-	-	-	1
Laboratory		Sand (80-160 µm)			-	-	-	1
Peñaflor	Non-Gypseus	Loam soil	F	CT, RT, NT	9	9	9	9
Bujalaloz	Gypseous	Sandy loam to clay loam	F, C, MB	CT	24	-	40	-
	Non-gypseous	Loam to silty clay loam	F, C, MB	CT	22	-	37	-
Belchite	Gypseous	Sandy loam	N	NG	8	-	8	-
		Sandy loam	N	GR	12	-	12	-
Leciñena	Gypseous	Sandy loam	N	NG	4	-	4	-
		Sandy loam	N	GR	8	-	8	-
Sariñena	Non-gypseous	Sandy loam	N	NG	5	-	5	-
		Loam	N	GR	7	-	8	-
Codo	Non-gypseous	Loam	N	GR	8	-	8	-

3 ¹ MB, F and C are freshly mouldboard tilled, cropped and fallowed cultivated soils, respectively, and N means uncultivated soil

4 ² CT, RT and NT are conventional, reduce and no tillage treatment, and NG and G are ungrazed and grazed soils, respectively.

5 ³ Surface crust.

6 ⁴ Contact sand layer between disc base and soil surface.

7

8

9

10

1 **Table 3.** Hydraulic parameters estimated from synthetic infiltration curves and objective function (Q) for the following scenarios: (a) inversion of
2 synthetic data for soils without sand layer and using NSH standard analysis, (b) inversion of synthetic data for soils with sand layer using NSH
3 standard analysis and (c) inversion of synthetic data for soils with sand layer using NSH with layered flow analysis.

Soil n°		Scenario (a)		Scenario (b)		Scenario (c)	
		Average [Confidence interval] ¹	Q	Average [Confidence interval]	Q	Average [Confidence interval]	Q
1	S (mm s ^{-0.5})	1.50 e+00 [1.50 e+00, 1.51 e+00]	3.19 e-02	-	-	-	-
	K (mm s ⁻¹)	1.00 e-01 [9.92 e-02, 1.01 e-01]					
2	S (mm s ^{-0.5})	3.66 e-01 [3.66 e-01, 3.67 e-01]	3.65 e-02	4.10 e-01 [4.10e-01, 4.11e-01]	2.59 e-01	3.49 e-01 [3.47 e-01, 3.50 e-01]	7.28 e-03
	K (mm s ⁻¹)	2.09 e-03 [2.05 e-03, 2.14 e-03]		1.91 e-05 [-2.91 e-04, 1.14 e-04]		2.82 e-03 [2.73 e-03, 2.90 e-03]	
3	S (mm s ^{-0.5})	2.39 e-01 [2.39 e-01, 2.40 e-01]	2.93 e-02	2.57 e-01 [2.56 e-01, 2.57 e-01]	5.21 e-01	2.35 e-01 [2.34 e-01, 2.35 e-01]	5.39 e-03
	K (mm s ⁻¹)	2.57 e-04 [2.38 e-04, 2.77 e-04]		3.20 e-06 [1.00e -05, 5.37 e-05]		4.17 e-04 [3.84 e-04, 4.52 e-04]	
4	S (mm s ^{-0.5})	2.87 e-01 [2.86 e-01, 2.87 e-01]	3.56 e-02	3.82 e-01 [3.81 e-01, 3.83 e-01]	2.42 e-01	3.16 e-01 [3.14 e-01, 3.17 e-01]	1.05 e-02
	K (mm s ⁻¹)	9.12 e-03 [9.07 e-03, 9.20 e-03]		5.01 e-03 [4.91 e-03, 5.16 e-03]		9.33 e-03 [9.20 e-03, 9.47 e-03]	
5	S (mm s ^{-0.5})	2.27 e-01 [2.27 e-01, 2.28 e-01]	1.39 e-01	3.05 e-01 [3.04 e-01, 3.06 e-01]	2.91 e-01	2.48 e-01 [2.46 e-01, 2.49 e-01]	8.29 e-03
	K (mm s ⁻¹)	3.47 e-03 [3.45 e-03, 3.49 e-03]		2.99 e-03 [2.95 e-03, 3.05 e-03]		4.37 e-03 [4.31 e-03, 4.42 e-03]	
6	S (mm s ^{-0.5})	2.11 e-01 [2.00 e-01, 2.13 e-01]	4.92 e-01	2.90e-01 [2.89 e-01, 2.91 e-01]	2.14 e-01	2.43 e-01 [2.41e-01, 2.45e-01]	1.29 e-02
	K (mm s ⁻¹)	6.61 e-03 [6.54 e-03, 6.63 e-03]		7.24 e-03 [7.21 e-03, 7.32 e-03]		8.13 e-03 [8.06 e-03, 8.20 e-03]	
7	S (mm s ^{-0.5})	6.41 e-01 [6.37 e-01, 6.46 e-01]	1.76 e-01	6.66 e-01 [6.63 e-01, 6.69 e-01]	1.37 e-01	6.30 e-01 [6.14 e-01, 6.44 e-01]	1.76 e-01
	K (mm s ⁻¹)	6.03 e-02 [6.00 e-02, 6.07 e-02]		6.03 e-02 [6.00 e-02, 6.05 e-02]		5.89 e-02 [5.81 e-02, 5.96 e-02]	
8	S (mm s ^{-0.5})	7.13 e-01 [7.04 e-01, 7.19 e-01]	2.81 e-01	7.08 e-01 [7.05 e-01, 7.14 e-01]	1.11 e-01	6.75 e-01 [6.54 e-01, 6.88 e-01]	1.95 e-01
	K (mm s ⁻¹)	7.08 e-02 [7.04 e-02, 7.13 e-02]		6.61 e-02 [6.58 e-02, 6.64 e-02]		6.46 e-02 [6.38 e-02, 6.55 e-02]	
9	S (mm s ^{-0.5})	7.70 e-01 [7.68 e-01, 7.72 e-01]	4.90 e-02	7.06 e-01 [7.01 e-01, 7.10 e-01]	1.04 e-02	7.06 e-01 [7.01 e-01, 7.10 e-01]	1.04 e-02
	K (mm s ⁻¹)	3.39 e-02 [3.36 e-02, 3.42 e-02]		3.89 e-02 [3.84 e-02, 3.94 e-02]		3.89 e-02 [3.84 e-02, 3.94 e-02]	
10	S (mm s ^{-0.5})	3.45 e+00 [3.44 e+00, 3.45 e+00]	1.89 e-02	-	-	-	-
	K (mm s ⁻¹)	2.82 e-02 [2.44 e-02, 3.21 e-02]					
11	S (mm s ^{-0.5})	9.27 e-01 [9.25 e-01, 9.30 e-01]	3.93 e-02	1.04 e+00 [1.03 e+00, 1.04 e+00]	1.70 e-01	9.02 e-01 [8.98 e-01, 9.07 e-01]	1.95 e-01
	K (mm s ⁻¹)	2.34 e-02 [2.32 e-02, 2.38 e-02]		1.35 e-02 [1.31 e-02, 1.41 e-02]		6.46 e-02 [6.38 e-02, 6.55 e-02]	
12	S (mm s ^{-0.5})	1.03 e+00 [1.03 e+00, 1.03 e+00]	3.67 e-02	1.11 e+00 [1.11 e+00, 1.12 e+00]	1.74 e-01	9.57 e-01 [9.53 e-01, 9.61 e-01]	1.07 e-02
	K (mm s ⁻¹)	1.33 e-02 [1.29 e-02, 1.39 e-02]		4.37 e-06 [1.00 e-05, 6.31 e-04]		2.11 e-02 [2.05 e-02, 2.20 e-02]	

¹ Confidence interval estimated considering uncertainty due to water level measurement (± 0.5 mm) for a 1.6 cm diameter reservoir.

4
5

1

2 **Table 4.** Soil sorptivity (S) and hydraulic conductivity (K) estimated with a 10 cm diameter disc infiltrometer in four different fields
3 in Bujaraloz, Peñafior and Codo with the DL and the NSH methods. Q and t_{sand} denotes the objective function (Eq. 13) and the time
4 to saturate the contact sand layer, respectively. Within square bracket, the average confidence interval estimated with NSH
5 considering uncertainty due to water level measurement (± 0.5 mm) for a 1.6 cm diameter reservoir.

Location	Field	DL				NSH			
		S (mm s^{-05})	K (mm s^{-1})	R ²	t_{sand} (s)	S (mm s^{-05})	K (mm s^{-1})	Q	t_{sand} (s)
Bujaraloz	CAL006_NC_R ₁	0.51	0.0428	0.81	10-15	0.43 [0.422-0.431]	0.0422 [0.0418-0.0426]	0.091	4
Peñafior	SD_1_MF	0.29	0.0270	0.22	5-10	0.36 [0.359-0.366]	0.0110 [0.0103-0.0116]	0.069	2
Codo	Plan_past_NC_R ₈	1.26	-0.2431	0.12	5-10	0.34 [0.339-0.348]	0.0007 [0.0001-0.001]	0.150	5
Bujaraloz	03_NC_R2	1.04	-0.0079	0.03	5-10	0.64 [0.637 0.644]	0.0083 [0.0072-0.0097]	0.570	4

6

7

8

9

1

2

3

4

5

6 **Figure 1.**

7

1

2 **Figure 2.**

1

2

3

4 **Figure 3.**

5

1

2

3

4

5

6 **Figure 4.**

7

1

2 **Figure 5.**

3

1

2

3 **Figure 6.**

1

a

b

2

3

4 Figure 7.

5

1

2
3

4 **Figure 8.**

5

1

2

3 **Figure 9**

1

2 **Fig. 10.**

1

2

3

4

5

6 **Fig. 11**

7